

with cold dil. HCl (25 ml) precipitated a white compound. It was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried in vacuum and finally crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 180°, yield 60%.

The compound was soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gave colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

Adopting the above procedure compounds **Ib** to **Ij** were prepared.

Preparation of cyclopropane derivatives of Ia (IIa) :

4,4'-Bis-benzylidene-2-pyrazolin-5-thiones (8 g) was dissolved in 20% NaOH solution (25 ml). To it a saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide (30 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for 2 hr. The brownish compound precipitated out was filtered, washed with 20% sodium thiosulphate solution and then with distilled water. It was dried in vacuum and finally crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 64°, yield 50%.

The compound was soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gave no colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

Adopting the above procedure compounds **IIb** to **IIj** were prepared.

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Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of Some Substituted 4-Thiazolidinones and Their Benzoyl Derivatives

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4-THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives are known to possess a variety of physiological properties, viz., anticonvulsant¹, sciatic nerve block², spiral anaes-

thesia³, CNS-stimulant⁴, local anaesthetic⁵, analgesic⁶, choleric⁷, sedative⁸, antiphlogistic⁹ activities.

With a view of preparing better therapeutic agents, we have synthesised 4-thiazolidinones of type (I) containing nitrophenol residue by the action of thioglycolic acid, thiolactic acid or thiomalic acid on Schiff bases obtained by condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro-benzophenone⁸ with different sulpho drugs. The structures were supported by ir spectra¹⁰⁻¹³.

I

R = H, pyrimidyl, 4'-methyl pyrimidyl, 4',6'-dimethyl pyrimidyl, 2'-thiazolyl or 3',4'-dimethyl oxazolyl.

R₁ = H, OH, OH₂COOH
R₂ = H, OOC₂H₅

The ir spectra of 4-thiazolidinones (I) were taken in KBr pellets. The C=O group frequency was obtained at 1630, N-CO at 1575, phenolic OH at 3415 and NHSO₂ at 1160 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

Preparation of α-phenyl-2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro benzalanyl-2-benzoate : 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro-benzophenone (0.01 mole) dissolved in ethanol was added to sulphanilamides (0.01 mole) in ethanol and refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. The content was poured into water. The product was separated and crystallised from ethanol. The anils were benzoylated by treatment with benzoyl chloride and 10% cold sodium hydroxide solution. The product was poured on ice, separated and crystallised from ethanol. (R₂ = H; yield 68%, m.p. 110°). (Found : C, 56.96; H, 4.00; N, 9.94. C₂₀H₁₇O₅N₃S requires C, 57.00; H, 4.04; N, 9.98%).

Other anils were prepared similarly. The physical constants and antimicrobial data of the anils are given in Table 1.

Preparation of α-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-3'-nitro phenyl)-3-p-amino sulphophenyl-4-thiazolidinone : α-Phenyl-2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro benzal anil (0.01 mole) in benzene was refluxed with thioglycolic acid (0.01 mole) on a water bath for 4 hr. The product was crystallised from ethanol, yield 58%, m.p. 140°. (Found : C, 54.40; N, 3.88; H, 8.63. C₂₃H₁₆O₅N₃S₂ requires C, 54.43; H, 3.92; N, 8.66%).

Similarly, other anils were treated with thioglycolic acid.

Preparation of α-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-3'-nitro phenyl)-3-p-amino sulphophenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone : Thiolactic acid (0.01 mole) was added to a saturated solution of α-phenyl-2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro benzal anil (0.01 mole) in dry benzene

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NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND ANTIMICROBIAL DATA OF ANILS

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Zone of inhibition* (24 hr)	
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₃ S	110	68	14	7
2.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₃ S	120	55	12	7
3.	Pyrimidyl	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₅ S	135	70	11	6
4.	Pyrimidyl	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₁ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₅ S	160	65	12	6
5.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	H	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₅ S	173	50	10	8
6.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₃ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₅ S	185	70	13	6
7.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	H	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₅ S	125	65	64	—
8.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₅ S	165	65	15	6
9.	2'-Thiazolyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	202	58	9	—
10.	2'-Thiazolyl	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	198	55	12	7
11.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	H	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₃ S	145	63	10	7
12.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ O ₆ N ₃ S	175	65	14	4

* in mm.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL CONSTANT AND ANTIMICROBIAL DATA OF 4-THIAZOLIDINONE OF TYPE I

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Zone of inhibition in mm (24 hr)	
							<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	H	H	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	140	58	16	7
2.	H	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	130	60	17	8
3.	H	CH ₃	H	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	120	65	17	5
4.	H	OH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₇ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	165	60	13	4
5.	H	CH ₂ COOH	H	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	108	68	14	—
6.	H	CH ₂ COOH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₁ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	125	70	21	—
7.	Pyrimidyl	H	H	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	140	72	23	6
8.	Pyrimidyl	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₃ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	170	68	15	6
9.	Pyrimidyl	OH	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	160	65	18	5
10.	Pyrimidyl	OH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	185	70	15	5
11.	Pyrimidyl	CH ₂ COOH	H	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	150	65	24	—
12.	Pyrimidyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₃ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	170	60	14	6
13.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	H	H	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	195	65	17	—
14.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	205	60	17	5
15.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	CH ₃	H	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	208	70	18	5
16.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	OH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₅ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	209	68	13	6
17.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	CH ₂ COOH	H	C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	195	67	14	8
18.	4',6'-Dimethyl pyrimidyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₅ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	210	70	11	—
19.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	H	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	129	67	9	—
20.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	167	65	12	6
21.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	CH ₃	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	198	70	15	4
22.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	OH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	170	58	15	6
23.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	CH ₂ COOH	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	182	65	12	4
24.	4'-Methyl pyrimidyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₅ S ₂	185	70	10	4
25.	2'-Thiazolyl	H	H	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	205	65	14	—
26.	2'-Thiazolyl	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	198	60	12	5
27.	2'-Thiazolyl	CH ₃	H	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	203	68	17	11
28.	2'-Thiazolyl	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₂ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	215	70	18	—
29.	2'-Thiazolyl	CH ₂ COOH	H	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	212	65	15	—
30.	2'-Thiazolyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₂ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	208	62	14	—
31.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	H	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	178	58	16	9
32.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	H	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	180	60	15	8
33.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	OH	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	157	65	15	8
34.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	OH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₄ H ₂₉ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	175	65	14	6
35.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	CH ₂ COOH	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	155	67	19	—
36.	3',4'-Dimethyl oxazolyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₆ H ₅ CO	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ O ₆ N ₃ S ₂	172	58	21	—

All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

(25 ml) and refluxed for 6 hr. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, yield 65%, m.p. 120°. (Found : C, 55.27 ; H, 4.18 ; N, 8.40. C₂₃H₂₁O₆N₃S₂ requires C, 55.31 ; H, 4.21 ; N, 8.42%).

Similarly, other anils were treated with thiolactic acid.

Preparation of α-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-3'-nitro phenyl)-3-p-amino sulphophenyl-5-carboxymethyl-

4-thiazolidinone : α-Phenyl-2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro benzalanil (0.01 mole) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mole) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 30 min (Reddellien method¹⁴). The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate, reprecipitated with acid and crystallised from ethanol, yield 68%, m.p. 108°. (Found : C, 53.04 ; H, 3.87 ; N, 7.73. C₂₄H₂₁O₆N₃S₂ requires C, 53.00 ; H, 3.82 ; N, 7.70%).

Similarly, other anils were treated with thiomalic acid.

The physical constants and antimicrobial data of the compounds thus prepared are given in Table 2.

Antimicrobial screening :

The purified products were screened for antimicrobial activity by cup plate method¹ using *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The testing was carried out in ethanol solution at a concentration 10 mg/ml. The zone of inhibition of the test solution (0.5 mg) was recorded. Most of the anils are active against gram positive bacteria only while 4-thiazolidinones, containing 5-H/methyl were active against both gram positive and gram negative.

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Biological Activity of 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-p-azobenzene Sulphonamido Thiazoles

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AZO dyes are well known for their antiseptic activity^{1,2} and some are useful as chemotherapeutic agents³. A number of thiazole compounds have been tested for antibacterial⁴, antifungal⁵, antitumor⁶ and anthelmintic activity⁷. Sulphonamides are known antibacterial agents. Since 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole has been reported to possess antifungal activity⁸ and some 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazoles are reported to possess possible anticancer activity⁹,

coupling of diazotized sulphonamide with 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole was expected to yield compounds with increased antibacterial, antifungal and anticancer activity. With this in view, various sulphonamides were prepared to yield compounds (I) and to study their biological activities.

The compound (I) described here have been synthesized by reacting the diazotized sulphonamides with 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole by the established method⁹. The structure of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analysis and ir spectral studies and homogeneity by tlc technique.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded by KBr disc method on Perkin-Elmer 377 IR spectrophotometer and uv spectra on Beckman DU₂ spectrophotometer. TLC was done using silica gel G as adsorbent and chloroform-methanol (85 : 15) as solvent.

Preparation of 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-p-azobenzene sulphonamido thiazole (I; R=H): The sulphonamide (0.01 mole) was dissolved in 3 equivalent of hydrochloric acid and the solution was cooled to 0-5°. A cold solution of sodium nitrite (0.02 mole) was added dropwise with stirring. After completion of the reaction any excess of nitrous acid was destroyed by careful addition of urea. 2-Amino-4-phenyl thiazole (0.01 mole) was dissolved in alcohol (25 ml) and sodium acetate (0.01 mole) was added. The solution was cooled to 0-5°. To this, the solution of diazonium salt of sulphonamide was added with stirring. A bright coloured product was obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol-DMF mixture. All the compounds gave characteristic peaks $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ between 1648-1520 (aromatic nuclei, C=N, C=C and N=N) and 1355-1335, 1165-1150 cm^{-1} (SO_2NH) and show $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ at 270 nm. (Compound 1, m.p. 246-247°; Found: N, 19.32. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$; N, 19.49%).

The analysis data of the compounds prepared are given in Table 1.

Preliminary antimicrobial and antifungal activity was studied by disc diffusion plate method. 1 : 500 and 1 : 1000 solutions of the test compounds were made in Tween 80-water (20 : 80). A control was run simultaneously. Moderate to feeble antibacterial activity was recorded against *Proteus vulgaris*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus lutea*. No antifungal activity was shown by the compounds when tested against *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus nigrican* and *Helminthosporium aptilinae*